

Policy Brief

Blue Economy and nature-based solutions: A sustainable future for Atlantic Industries

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Executive Summary

This policy brief highlights the urgent need to align scientific innovation with marine policy, enhance transatlantic cooperation across Europe, Africa, and South America, and accelerate the uptake of bio-based and nature-based solutions to support a Sustainable Blue Economy. Despite a robust framework of international and European policies, implementation remains fragmented, with limited integration of scientific knowledge into policy.

Marine microbiomes represent a promising frontier for sustainability, offering new opportunities for environmental restoration and economic growth. However, realising their potential requires coherent regulatory frameworks and equitable access and benefit-sharing mechanisms. The AtlantECO project demonstrates the power of interdisciplinary research, collaborative innovation networks, and evidence-based policy to tackle ocean challenges across the Atlantic basin.

Key recommendations in this brief focus on reinforcing transatlantic collaboration, improving the science-policy interface, and building shared systems for ocean knowledge and innovation. These measures are essential to advancing climate resilience, ocean health, and equitable economic development throughout the All-Atlantic community. The brief ultimately aims to elevate awareness, build capacity, promote responsible practices, and catalyse a Blue Growth strategy that unites the All-Atlantic region, aligned with AtlantECO's mission.

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Background & Context

The Atlantic Ocean is at the core of the global maritime economy and a vital provider of ecosystem services. As human activity intensifies, the repercussions cascade across marine ecosystems, amplifying the impact of climate change, overexploitation, pollution, and other environmental stressors.

The AtlantECO project steps into this context by focusing on the structure and functioning of the Atlantic Ocean ecosystem, with particular emphasis on the **microbiome, plastics and the plastisphere**, and **seascape connectivity**. Recognising the lack of comprehensive knowledge about the Atlantic Ocean ecosystem's structure, functioning, health, and services, AtlantECO aims to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework for providing knowledge-based resources to support decision-making, design policies, and engage with citizens to encourage responsible behaviour to manage the Atlantic system and protect its ecosystem services provision.

Amid rapid population growth and accelerating climate change, a paramount challenge emerges: **preserving ecosystem services and good environmental status**. AtlantECO's efforts align with the **Atlantic Maritime Strategy**, which aspires to cultivate a sustainable Blue Economy in the Atlantic area, harmonising economic development with environmental preservation and climate adaptation.

Europe has introduced a range of policy incentives and frameworks to promote sustainable Blue Economy practices, particularly in alignment with the European Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the EU Blue Economy strategy. These incentives include funding programmes, regulatory frameworks, and innovation support mechanisms. Depending on the funding scheme, these tools can act at European-, regional-, national-, and bilateral-levels.

The **European Ocean Pact** [1] was adopted on June 5, 2025, by the European Commission as a comprehensive strategy to address the challenges facing the ocean, including pollution, climate change, and overexploitation of marine resources. The Sustainable Blue Economy is one of the six priority areas.

The **EU Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy** [2] aims to promote sustainable growth in ocean-related economic activities while protecting the marine environment. It is a key part of the European Green Deal, aligning marine activities with climate and environmental goals. The strategy sets a vision for a climate-neutral, sustainable, and circular Blue Economy, focusing on decarbonising maritime transport, developing marine renewable energy, promoting circularity in sectors like fishing and ship recycling, and preserving coastal biodiversity. It encourages synergies between marine sectors and nature-based solutions (NbS).

The **EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030** [3] is a comprehensive plan to protect and restore nature across Europe, aiming to reverse biodiversity loss by 2030. Key elements include protecting at least 30% of land and sea in the EU, restoring degraded ecosystems, and addressing the drivers of biodiversity loss. The strategy also promotes restoration of marine ecosystems as essential to a resilient Blue Economy, supporting the integration of NbS into coastal zone management.

Portugal, Ireland, France, and Spain have national Blue Economy strategies or roadmaps aligned with EU goals. The **Atlantic Maritime Strategy** and related action plans [4] promote cross-border cooperation and innovation in the Atlantic basin.

Alongside strategic frameworks and regulatory developments, the European Union has mobilised substantial funding and financing mechanisms to catalyse the transition toward a Sustainable Blue Economy and accelerate marine-based innovation. The **European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)** allocates €6.1 billion (2021-2027) to support sustainable fisheries, aquaculture, and Blue Economy innovation. Managed primarily through national programmes co-financed by the EU and Member States, EMFAF supports eco-innovation, coastal resilience, marine biodiversity restoration, and adaptation to climate change. Under its directly managed instruments, EMFAF also launched the **BlueInvest initiative**, which blends public and private capital to support early-stage Blue Economy SMEs and startups.

Horizon Europe, the EU's flagship research and innovation programme, supports sustainable ocean solutions under **Cluster 6 - Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment**. This includes targeted investments in biodiversity and ecosystem services, clean environment and zero pollution, and sustainable bio-based systems. Particular emphasis is placed on the development of NbS, circular economy practices, marine biotechnology, and the creation of sustainable blue value chains. Under **Cluster 5 - Climate, Energy, and Mobility**, Horizon Europe targets climate neutrality in the maritime sector, including offshore renewable energy, decarbonisation of maritime transport, and climate adaptation strategies for coastal and marine areas, all crucial for the Sustainable Blue Economy.

Complementing these efforts, the **EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"** aims to protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems by integrating research and innovation with citizen engagement and blue investments. By addressing the ocean and inland waters as a single interconnected system, the Mission Ocean plays a central role in achieving the EU's climate neutrality and biodiversity goals.

Despite these advances, the ocean governance landscape remains fragmented, with overlapping jurisdictions, regulatory inconsistencies, and gaps between policy ambition and implementation. Global frameworks such as the **United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)** and the **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)** provide foundational legal regimes for marine governance, environmental protection, and equitable access to genetic resources. The **Nagoya Protocol** (2010) and the recently adopted **Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement** (2023) address critical gaps in the sustainable use and benefit-sharing of marine genetic resources, including those relevant to microbiome research. Within the EU, instruments like the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)** and the **Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)** support regional marine conservation and resource management.

However, the uptake of innovative, sustainable solutions remains weak, often hindered by limited policy coherence, insufficient integration of scientific knowledge, and underdeveloped mechanisms for cross-border collaboration and benefit-sharing. The **UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030)** offers an opportunity to improve ocean knowledge, foster international collaboration, and strengthen science-policy interfaces, although it is not legally binding.

Addressing these policy and implementation gaps is essential to realizing the goals of the Sustainable Blue Economy and ensuring that innovations in areas, such as microbiome research and bio-based solutions, contribute meaningfully to ocean health and resilience.

02

Introduction

Sustainable Blue Economy refers to the sustainable use of ocean and water resources for economic growth, scientific and technological innovation, improved livelihoods, and job creation, while preserving the health of marine and freshwater ecosystems. The Blue Economy includes all activities that are marine-based or marine-related, encompassing not only traditional sectors but also emerging and innovative sectors, i.e. less mature industries linked to the marine environment, which bring new opportunities for investment and hold potential for future development of coastal communities. These include offshore renewable energy, aquaculture, seabed extractive activities, marine biotechnology and bioprospecting.

Recognising the potential to make a significant contribution to economic growth, job creation, and sustainability transition, the EU has established 12 Blue Economy sectors [5]:

With an annual economic value estimated at €2.3 trillion, ocean-linked sectors, or the 'Blue Economy' is equivalent to the world's 7th largest economy [6]. In 2020, the export value of the ocean economy was €1.2 trillion, with exports of ocean-based goods estimated to be €619 billion, and exports of ocean-based services €571 billion. When looking at the top ocean economy exporters, the European Union is by far the biggest exporter of ocean-based goods and services, with €417 billion of exports in 2020 [7].

According to 2022 data, the established sectors of the EU Blue Economy directly employed close to 4.82 million people and generated around €890.6 billion in turnover and €250.7 billion in gross value added (GVA). Furthermore, the estimates suggest that the EU Blue Economy sectors continued to grow in 2023, contributing €263 billion to the EU GVA and employing 4.88 million persons. Between 2012 and 2022, the Blue Economy's real GVA grew by an estimated 37%, accounting for 2% of total EU GVA growth during this period [8].

Coastal tourism remains the largest blue economy sector, generating 33% of the EU Blue Economy GVA and 53% of total EU Blue Economy's employment in 2022. The EU offshore wind energy sector is one of the fastest growing sectors in the EU economy, with a 42% increase in GVA compared to 2021. This growth boosted the sector's profits, which reached €4.1 billion in 2022 [8].

The 2025 edition of the EU Blue Economy report [8] places special focus on the energy transition in EU maritime transport and the fishing fleet, as well as the potential of NbS against the impacts of climate change in EU coastal areas. NbS provides opportunities to strengthen coastal protection and reduce the risks of flooding and coastal erosion. Coastal flooding causes economic damages of € 1.2 billion per year in the EU [9]. By 2100, annual damages could reach €1 trillion, with 3.9 million people exposed to coastal flooding every year in Europe [10] [11] [12].

NbS has been gaining increasing attention as a resilient and adaptable strategy for safeguarding coastlines. Compared with traditional engineering approaches, they can be more sustainable and cost-effective, leveraging natural processes and ecosystems such as wetlands, mangroves, dunes, and reefs, to reduce the impacts of coastal flooding and erosion while simultaneously enhancing biodiversity and supporting local communities. By integrating ecological restoration with human infrastructure needs, these approaches not only provide physical protection but also contribute to carbon sequestration, water quality improvement, and recreational opportunities, making them a holistic solution for coastal resilience.

In light of the environmental repercussions of human activities, political action was taken to define a Sustainable Blue Economy, as the EU is fostering the transition to a Sustainable Blue Economy as part of the European Green Deal. This approach guarantees coherence across the Blue Economy sectors, facilitating their coexistence and synergies within the maritime space, without harming or compromising the health of the environment. The EU has been promoting the Sustainable Blue Economy as a central motor in alleviating the pressures on natural resources and fostering climate change mitigation and adaptation. In this context, the need to develop and promote Sustainable Blue Economy activities has become critical.

03

Microbiomes and Bio-Based Innovation

Marine microbiomes are emerging as key assets in the Blue Economy and NbS. These microscopic ecosystems - complex communities of microorganisms such as bacteria, archaea, fungi, protists, and metazoans - play vital roles in nutrient cycling, climate regulation, and the health of marine species and habitats. Advances in DNA sequencing and bioinformatics are now unlocking the potential of microbiomes for bio-based innovation across sectors, including aquaculture, bioremediation, pharmaceuticals, and sustainable materials.

Marine biological prospecting includes the discovery of novel genes and biological compounds from the ocean environment that can lead to commercial development of pharmaceuticals, enzymes, cosmetics, biodegradable plastics and other products. There is growing commercial interest in marine genetic resources, with patent applications increasing rapidly at rates exceeding 12% per year. A majority of these patents have been filed by a few highly developed countries, highlighting the increasing biotechnology capacity gap between nations [13]. Recent research reveals that marine gene sequences referenced in patent filings are quite numerous. A 2018 study reported 12,998 sequences from 862 marine species [14]. More recent analyses, however, show a sharp increase in marine genetic data associated with patent activity. The MArine Bioprospecting PATent (MABPAT) database (2024) identifies over 92,550 protein-coding sequences linked to 4,779 patent filings, spanning more than 1,000 marine species [15]. This rapid growth reflects the expanding commercial interest in marine genetic resources and underscores the need for robust governance frameworks ensuring equitable access, benefit sharing, and responsible innovation in marine biotechnology.

For Atlantic countries, investing in marine microbiome research and infrastructure can catalyse high-value innovation, promote ecosystem resilience, and support the development of sustainable, biotechnology-driven industries. To ensure fair access and benefit-sharing from microbiome resources, coherent regulatory frameworks and multilateral cooperation are essential, especially in transboundary marine regions.

Capacity-building and technology transfer relating to marine bioprospecting are likely to increase with the ongoing implementation of the Nagoya Protocol to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), under which researchers expecting to commercialize natural products are required to share benefits with the host country. These benefits include both monetary and non-monetary benefits; the latter generally consist of partnerships between researchers in developing and industrial countries, capacity building, and the transfer of appropriate technologies (for example, setting up laboratory facilities in low- and middle-income countries universities) [13].

Developing countries are faced with scientific capacity challenges, including a lack of expertise in taxonomy, difficulties in attracting and retaining qualified marine scientists, and limited research facilities and financial resources. Information sharing, capacity building, and the transfer of technology, including through the participation of developing states in research activities, are considered essential to address the general lack of scientific and other knowledge on marine genetic resources in these countries. Research collaborations between institutions from industrial and low- and middle-income countries have provided both training opportunities and technology transfer, although such collaborations have so far been ad hoc and somewhat limited in scope [13].

Building on these foundational needs and opportunities, the AtlantECO project exemplifies how

transdisciplinary, collaborative research can drive sustainable blue bio-based innovation. The project combines oceanography, molecular biology, data science, and socioeconomics to deepen understanding and assessment of ecosystem services in the Atlantic. Using multiple platforms and technologies, including phenomics, the project fills critical knowledge and geographic gaps by integrating large-scale imaging and genetic data with environmental datasets. This supports the development of new ocean indicators and improves predictive models, contributing towards the Ocean Digital Twin [16], ultimately contributing to more informed, sustainable marine governance across the Atlantic. With a special focus on the role of microbiomes in regulating key ecosystems, AtlantECO leverages the contribution of these microscopic communities to ocean health and resilience, as well as to sustainable innovations in biotechnology, aquaculture, and environmental remediation.

AtlantECO also fosters pan-Atlantic Innovation Networks to strengthen cooperation between public and private stakeholders around shared Blue Growth goals. These networks aim to promote knowledge exchange across Europe, Africa, and South America on key socio-economic issues, supporting more sustainable and resilient ocean management strategies, including Blue Economy and NbS.

To clearly demonstrate the exploitation potential of AtlantECO knowledge towards a range of applications, five case studies have been defined within the project, two of which demonstrate the applicability of sustainable Blue Economy and NbS methods, technologies, results, and outputs for real applications.

1

The **Molecular Bioprospecting** case study focuses on the discovery of new enzymes digesting microplastics, as well as enzymes with high-value applications in diagnosis and molecular research. Relevant industry stakeholders are directly involved in the exploitation phase as 'early adopters' of these specific project results.

2

The **Bioprospecting for organisms and impact of drilling in Brazil** case study collaborates with the industry to bioprospect microbial genes involved in hydrocarbon degradation near oil extraction sites, aiming to develop bioremediation tools. It also evaluates offshore oil drilling impacts through field studies and laboratory experiments exposing plankton to drilling materials. This work aims to inform future regulations and best practices in the gas and oil industry.

Together, these efforts illustrate how AtlantECO operationalises marine microbiome research and bio-based innovation to support a sustainable Blue Economy and resilient nature-based solutions across the Atlantic region.

04

Key recommendations

Ensuring the sustainability of the oceans is fundamental not only for maintaining marine biodiversity but also for securing the future of human endeavours that rely on the ocean's health. Realising the full benefits of a Sustainable Blue Economy will depend greatly on enhanced cooperation across the Atlantic, especially between the European Union, African and South American nations. These territories are intrinsically linked by shared marine systems, migratory patterns, climatic influences, and common economic and social interests in coastal and oceanic environments. By uniting around common sustainability objectives, they can create stronger and more inclusive frameworks that protect the marine environment while advancing prosperity and fairness.

1

Give precedence to the co-creation of evidence-led policies for ocean governance, facilitate the exchange of marine technologies, strengthening of local capacities, and synchronising efforts to track biodiversity and combat pollution. Cooperating through joint scientific efforts, mutual learning platforms, and standardised regulations is essential to address cross-border issues like unregulated fishing, marine ecosystem decline, pollution, and climate-driven changes to the ocean.

2

Reinforce the interface between scientific research and policy development to strengthen cooperation at the Atlantic scale. Integrate science more effectively into governance frameworks to ensure that decisions are grounded in the latest evidence and reflect the complexity of marine ecosystems. This requires creating more structured and inclusive pathways for dialogue between researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders across regions, facilitating mutual understanding, responsiveness to emerging knowledge, and shared responsibility for sustainable ocean stewardship.

3

Develop shared systems for ocean knowledge and innovation that transcend national boundaries. Establish open, interoperable data platforms, collaborative research infrastructures, and co-designed monitoring strategies to improve the way scientific insights inform marine governance. Such transatlantic knowledge hubs would not only enhance transparency and policy coherence, but also enable more equitable access to data, tools, and technologies, particularly benefiting countries with limited scientific capacity. In doing so, they would contribute to a more integrated and resilient Atlantic community, united by a common commitment to protecting ocean health and fostering sustainable development.

05

Conclusions

The health and resilience of the Atlantic Ocean are foundational to the well-being of its bordering nations and the global community. However, fragmented governance, limited integration of scientific knowledge, and weak uptake of innovative solutions continue to hinder progress toward sustainability. The AtlantECO project has demonstrated that a transdisciplinary, cooperative, and science-informed approach can effectively overcome many of these challenges.

To unlock the full potential of a Sustainable Blue Economy, countries on both sides of the Atlantic must deepen collaboration, embrace bio-based innovation, and ensure policies are driven by up-to-date science and supported by inclusive governance frameworks. Marine microbiomes, in particular, represent an untapped asset for both environmental restoration and economic opportunity, but their responsible use demands clear access and benefit-sharing mechanisms.

Building a shared knowledge system, reinforcing the science-policy interface, and promoting inclusive, cross-border innovation networks are essential steps forward. This policy brief calls for sustained investment in these areas to ensure that the Atlantic becomes a model of marine stewardship — resilient, equitable, and grounded in scientific understanding.

06

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